

End-to-End Slice Orchestration in a 5G cloud-native Mobile Network with O-RAN Split 7.2

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Abstract—The adoption of novel network paradigms in the architecture and management of mobile networks is accelerating its evolution. In this demonstration, we contribute to the cloud-native mobile network orchestration domain by presenting an end-to-end system allowing the disaggregated and distributed deployment of mobile network entities from core to RAN based on open-source software. The distinguishing features of this system are the possibility of enabling the configuration of slices that can be later activated on-demand and the use of O-RAN Split 7.2 for over-the-air transmission using commercial equipment.

Index Terms—B5G/6G, Slicing, Management and Orchestration, Cloud-Native, Split 7.2, Open5GS, srsRAN

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of cloud-native principles together with new architectural concepts, like disaggregation and slicing in the mobile core and RAN segments, are enabling a significant transformation in the architecture and management of Beyond 5G and 6G networks, allowing unprecedented scalability, adaptability, and efficiency. To achieve maximum potential, it is of paramount importance to design suitable management and orchestration (MANO) procedures to automate these deployments and cater the benefits of an efficient use of assigned networking resources to the different created slices and computing resources distributed across different points of presence (PoPs).

Despite significant advances in MANO and slicing research in recent years, practical implementations of systems capable of orchestrating slices in mobile networks remain limited in the literature. For example, [1] introduces an orchestrated sliced mobile network utilizing virtual machines for the mobile core based on Open5GS and a physical gNB powered by Amarisoft. Building on this, [2] extends the field with an end-to-end (E2E) cloud-native approach incorporating also the RAN segment, using OpenAirInterface software and Split 8 over-the-air (OTA) transmission.

This demonstration advances research in the cloud-native orchestration of sliced mobile networks by showcasing a practical implementation of a fully disaggregated and distributed deployment of an E2E open-source cloud-native mobile network. The novelty of the system lies in its support for flexible slice configuration and integration of O-RAN Split 7.2 into the RAN

segment, achieving an optimal balance between fronthaul capacity and the complexity of commercial O-Radio Unit (RU) equipment. The different entities of the mobile network are packaged as different Network Services (NSs) based on open-source software (i.e., Open5GS [3] and srsRAN [4]), which are managed by an ETSI NFV Management and Orchestration (MANO) stack to facilitate its automated deployment.

II. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 shows the experimental setup deployed in the EXTREME® xG Testbed located in CTTC (Castelldefels, Spain). This setup is distributed across four commercial off-the-shelf servers. One server executes our MANO system, powered by an instance of ETSI Open Source MANO (OSM) Release 14. The remaining three servers act as PoPs, and each one runs a single-node Kubernetes cluster. These three clusters represent the different tiers available in MNO deployments, i.e., central, regional, and edge cloud sites where NSs associated to the mobile network entities are running. In the RAN part, the edge cloud is connected to a Falcon RX/G O-RAN switch and Precision Time Protocol (PTP) grandmaster, providing the synchronization between the edge cloud and the O-RU, which is a LITEON FlexFi FF-RFI078I4¹. Finally, the setup is completed with two smartphones (Realme 9 and OnePlus 8 Pro), which are interfaced via a remote desktop tool (e.g., AnyDesk).

This demonstration shows the capabilities of this setup to create E2E slices in a full-cloud native open-source 5G mobile network including O-RAN Split 7.2 equipment. For that, based on the distributed cloud-native 5G mobile network deployment in [5], we developed four additional configuration blueprints (i.e., Helm charts). On the 5G core part, we have upgraded to *Open5GS v2.7.1* to generate one additional blueprint allowing the decoupling of the SMF entity from the control-plane blueprint to be able to configure and handle multiple slices. In the RAN part, we have generated two decoupled blueprints, one for the Central Unit (CU) and one for the Distributed Unit (DU) using srsRAN Release 24.12². The DU manifest is ready to configure and launch OTA transmission using the Split 7.2 open fronthaul interface through the LITEON FlexFi RU hardware. The synchronization provided by the Falcon Switch is acquired by launching the PTP blueprint running the

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¹The same setup has also been validated with a Benetel R550 RU.

²A patch has been applied to the source code to be able to run the containerised CU and DU entities in distributed machines.

Fig. 1. System Architecture under demonstration.

Linux *ptp4l* and *phc2sys* processes for our deployed setup. All blueprints for mobile network entities, whether from the core or the RAN segment, expose their internal NF pods for external access. This is accomplished through the Kubernetes *Load-Balancer* service type, enabling distributed deployment across various PoPs. Additionally, the flexible templating capabilities of Helm charts facilitate the parametrization of blueprints for the mobile core, CU, and DU, allowing the deployment of a mobile network with a customizable number of slices and configurations. These blueprints are further encapsulated in OSM descriptors (VNF and NS packages). The mentioned parametrization allows the generation of tailored configuration files to feed OSM instantiation commands, enabling the on-demand and flexible creation of instances of these entities.

III. DEMONSTRATION

This demonstration showcases the on-demand and distributed deployment of a fully disaggregated cloud-native 5G mobile network considering Split 7.2 between DU and RU with on-demand configuration of slices emulating different conditions of bandwidth and latency. The involved entities are packaged as different NSs. Initially, the multiple artefacts containing the disaggregated 5G core and O-RAN components are onboarded into the OSM MANO stack. The main steps of the demonstration are as follows:

- 1) We request our MANO system to deploy the PTP artefact in the *edge cloud* so that it can provide the tight synchronization required between DU and RU to the network interface connected to the Falcon fronthaul switch.
- 2) OSM receives the request from our MANO system to deploy the Open5GS control plane NS in the central cloud. We configure two slices for this deployment (i.e., SST:1 and SST:2). Once deployed, the UE information and its slice association are included in the UDR database. Then, we deploy the Open5GS user plane NSs (i.e., *SMF1*, *UPF1*) corresponding to slice #1 (i.e., SST:1) also in the *central cloud*.
- 3) Before deploying the RAN segment of the setup, we deploy the *RAN monitoring system* NS in the *regional cloud* to collect

RAN metrics from the DU instance, as described in [6].

- 4) Then, we proceed to deploy the disaggregated RAN components in the *regional and edge* clouds. It consists of two different NSs, the CU and the DU. Like with the core, the number of configured slices is set to two. Additionally, we specify the resources assigned to each of the requested slices in the DU.

- 5) Now, we proceed to register the UE_B in the network. After leaving flight mode, the UE_B receives an IP address in the range of the data network associated with slice#1, which is the configured slice for this UE.

- 6) OSM receives the request to deploy the second Open5GS user-plane NSs (i.e., *SMF2*, *UPF2*) in the *regional cloud* corresponding to slice#2 (SST:2). Then, we proceed to register UE_A in the network, which is associated to slice#2.

- 7) Finally, we start an iperf session between each UE and the UPF associated with its serving slice. The Grafana dashboard provides insights into the downlink (DL) metrics, showcasing the impact of the scheduler within the DU module as dictated by the slice configuration defined in step 4).

Throughout the demonstration, each step is visualized using the GUI of our OSM-powered MANO system, a remote desktop session displaying smartphone activity, and a Grafana dashboard highlighting the performance variations of UEs associated with different slices, as illustrated in Figure 1.

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